

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

Happy back to school!

By Santiago Cáceres Elvira

The new school year sometimes means new faces, and so it is with DATAMITE. I am Santiago Cáceres, project manager from [ITI](#) in Spain, and it is truly an honour to coordinate such an exciting project as DATAMITE.

The hard work continues! **Thank you for joining us and enjoy reading our newsletter!**

[Read the full article](#)

Article

How DATAMITE contributes to develop the common European data spaces?

How DATAMITE contributes to develop the common European data spaces

Practically every scenario of today's life produces data. This makes it important to create infrastructures where **data generated** by individuals, companies or public organisations **can be collected and shared easily, securely and ensuring the quality of the processed data**. This is the aim of the European Common Data Spaces. DATAMITE is an ally for the implementation of these common European data spaces.

[Learn how](#)

USE CASES

Use Case: Connecting eDWIN to data markets

The innovative services, more and more AI- based, require high quality of data but also a wide range of the trusted data sources from different providers. To be able to measure the value offered by the DATAMITE framework it is ideal to be tested over an actual use case where, despite the large amount of data already in operation, it is evident that secure **data exchange between public institutions**

and the commercial sector needs to be enabled to enhance data monetisation. **eDWIN**, a national platform for farming guidance in Poland, operated by **WODR** and **PSNC**, fulfils all the necessary requirements to be one of the Use Cases of the project.

[Discover more](#)

UPCOMING EVENTS

Join DATAMITE at the European Big Data Value forum

The **European Big Data Value Fomum (EBDVF) 2023** will take place in Valencia from 25 to 27 October. Organised by the Big Data Value Association (**BDVA**), it brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers. **DATAMITE is very proud to be one of the sponsors** of the EBDVF 2023, with a booth and co-organising the session “Data Sharing and Monetisation Platform Technology Enabling the Data Economy”.

[Discover more and join us!](#)

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